

OPTIMIZATION OF PROCESS PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT

This project investigates the parameters affecting the roughness of surfaces produced in the turning process for the material Al-Li 8090 alloy. Design of experiments was conducted for the analysis of the influence of the turning parameters such as cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut on the surface roughness. The results of the machining experiments for Al-Li 8090 alloy were used to characterize the main factors affecting surface roughness by the Taguchi method. The speed was found to be the most significant parameter influencing the surface roughness in the turning process. Otherwise, it include machining with minimum & optimum use of lubrication quantity.

KEYWORDS: Surface, Speed, Taguchi Method, Alloy

1. INTRODUCTION

Today's modern machining industries face challenge to achieve high quality in terms of work piece dimensional accuracy, surface finish, less wear on cutting tools, economy of machining in terms of cost saving. Surface roughness of the machined part is the most important criteria to judge the quality of operation. The literature survey has revealed that several researchers have attempted to calculate the optimum cutting conditions in a turning operation. Some of the other techniques which have been used to optimize the machining parameters include goal programming and geometrical programming.

1.1 TAGUCHI METHOD

Essentially, traditional experimental design procedures are too complicated and not easy to use. A large number of experimental works have to be carried out when the number of process parameters increases. To solve this problem, the Taguchi method uses a special design of orthogonal arrays to study the entire parameter space with only a small number of experiments

Taguchi is the developer of the Taguchi method. He proposed that engineering optimization of a process and product should be carried out in a three step approach, i.e. system design, tolerance design, and parameter design. In system design, the engineer applies scientific and engineering knowledge to produce a basic functional prototype design, this design including the product design stage and the process design stage. In the product design stage, the selection of materials and

components, tentative product parameter values, etc., are involved. As to the process design stage, the analysis of processing sequences, the selection of production equipment, tentative process parameter value, etc., are involved. Since system design is an initial functional design, it may be far from optimum in terms of quality and cost. Following on from system design is parameter design.

The objective of parameter design is to optimize the setting of the process parameter values for improving quality characteristics and to identify the product parameter values under the optimal process parameter values. In addition, it is expected that the optimal process parameter values obtained from parameter design are insensitive to variation in the environmental conditions and other noise factors.

Finally, tolerance design is used to determine and analyze tolerance around the optimal settings recommended by the parameter design. Tolerance design is required if the reduced variation obtained by the parameter design does not meet the required performance, and involves tightening tolerance on the product parameters or process parameters for which variations result in a large negative influence on the required product performance. Typically tightening tolerances means purchasing better-grade materials, components, or machinery, which increase cost. However based on the above discussions, parameter design is the key step in the Taguchi method to achieving high quality without increasing cost. To obtain high cutting performance in turning, the parameter design proposed by the Taguchi method is adopted in this paper.

1.2 MINIMUM QUANTITY LUBRICATION (MQL)

1.2.1 The Concept of MQL

In minimum quantity lubrication, a small volume of cutting fluid is transported to the cutting zone assisted by air and converted via orifices into small particles (atomization). These small particles are delivered to the cutting zone in the form of air borne particles, a gaseous suspension of liquid particles.

However, the ideal concept, is hard to achieve due to the air pressure accelerating the small particles and creating a mist. The working principle of MQL can be explained by using simple model depicted in figure.

FIGURE 1: IDEALIZED CONCEPT OF MQL

Oil in the reservoir is kept under constant pressure higher than in the mixing chamber. This pressure difference will make the oil flow up to the end of the nozzle where an orifice is located. The orifice has the main function of accelerating the particles' movement. As the particles' speed increases, the particles' size will be reduced. Smaller oil particles discharged from nozzle tip will subsequently be accelerated by the compressed air hence creating air borne particles. The lubricant in the form of air borne particles will have increased penetrability, especially to intrinsic (i.e. difficult to reach) areas. In this way, minute capillary created by two different surface asperities will help the small size particles of lubricant to gain access to the margined of the sliding and sticking areas. Additionally, the lubricant in the form of air borne particles will increase cooling capacity due to vaporization of lubricant particles.

FIGURE 2: A SIMPLE MODEL OF MQL SYSTEMS

1.2.2 The MQL System

In general, there are two types of MQL system. The first type is known as an internal system. In the internal system, oil and air is mixed in a mixing chamber before being delivered to the cutting zone through a single nozzle pipe. Meanwhile, the second type, or external system, an oil-air mixture

is carried out in the nozzle tip and the air borne particles are formed just after the nozzle tip. The oil is supplied in small quantities through a pipe to the nozzle tip where the air, flowing from a different pipe, will force the oil to the cutting zone. The difference between the external system (T-1) and internal system (T-2) are illustrated in figure.

As can be seen, from Figure, both systems work using an external nozzle that moves along in the cutting direction. This becomes a constraint for closed process such as drilling and boring, where the external nozzle will not provide sufficient cooling/ lubricating action deep into the drill tips. To address this obstacle, so that the MQL system can also be used for closed processes, an MQL system with an internal delivery system is the answer. With this system, whether for an internal or external mixing system, the air borne particles are transported to the cutting zone through a specially designed channel that is located inside the tool holder going through to the drill tip.

1.2.3 Application of Minimum Quantity Lubrication in Machining Processes

The application of the MQL method can be found in a variety of machining processes, especially in primary processes such as turning, drilling, milling, and grinding. In addition, cutting of wide varieties of workpiece material, such as aluminum, steel, hardened material as well as hard-to-cut material can also be done using the MQL method.

For instance, Sadeghi et al studied the grinding forces and surface quality properties of surface grinding AISI 4140 using the MQL application. They found that tangential cutting forces were lower using the MQL application compared to flood cooling and better surface finish can also be obtained with this method. In a related study using different workpiece material, 100 Cr6 hardened steel, Tawakoli et al identified that that a combination of the MQL method and resin bond corundum gave the best grinding performance in comparison to wet and dry machining. The two previous results supported the findings underlined by Da Silva et al. In terms of surface integrity (roughness, residual stress, micro hardness and microstructures), MQL can be utilized in grinding processes and achieves acceptable surface integrity. Moreover, drilling processes that are categorized as closed-type processes in machining applications have some constraints in respect of MQL application. This is due to the difficulty of air borne particles providing cooling or even lubrication to the drill tip; particularly during deep hole drilling. The preferred way is for internal cooling/ lubricating channels supplying coolant through an internal supply. These reduce cutting temperature by approximately 50% of compared to external coolant supply.

Heinemann et al stated that using an external nozzle for deep-hole twist drilling could be improved if a continuous coolant supply is changed to a discontinuous supply. This alternative method can further increase the cooling capacity thus helping tool wear reduction. In addition, the use of low viscosity cutting fluid can further improve penetration ability hence enabling cooling and/ lubricating action simultaneously.

It is more feasible to use MQL for drilling high thermal conductivity material, such as aluminum, rather than dry machining. High cutting temperatures, as in dry machining, would affect the hole quality due to thermal expansion. Therefore, MQL is preferable while overhead flood-cooling attempts should be avoided. By appropriate combination of machining variables, the performance can be equal to that of flood cooling for drilling aluminum.

Drilling and turning are prominent processes in the machining process due to being frequently used to produce round shaped components/parts. The turning process is classified as a process that produces continuous chips. This means the process will experience elevated temperatures. For decades, overhead flood cooling has been the only option, however, due to more stringent environmental policies, as well as the rising cost of cutting fluid acquisition, the utilization of this conventional method has been shifted to more environmentally friendly processes such as dry and near dry machining. MQL turning is one of the alternatives in respect of environmental prerequisites.

1.3 ALUMINUM LITHIUM ALLOY

Aluminum-lithium alloys (AL-Li) were developed primarily as direct replacements for existing aluminum alloys to reduce the weight of aircraft and aerospace structures. It has been realized that the most efficient way of doing this is to develop low density materials, since weight reduction through reduced component size often leads to low stiffness parts and reduced fatigue life. Typical components that benefit from low density alloys include structural members in airframes, aerospace vehicle skins, and liquid oxygen and hydrogen fuel tanks in spacecraft. Aluminum producers began major development of aluminum-lithium

alloys in the 1970s with the objective of introducing light weight, high stiffness aluminum alloys that could be fabricated on existing equipment and components could be handled and assembled using established techniques. Some of the most important commercial alloys in this class include 2090, 2091, 8090, and Weldalite 049 that were introduced in the 1980s. The table below shows the chemical composition of these alloys.

TABLE 1: COMPOSITION OF ALUMINUM-LITHIUM ALLOYS (WT. %)

Alloy	Cu	Li	Zr	Others
2090	2.7	2.2	0.12	-
2091	2.1	2.0	0.1	-
8090	1.3	2.45	0.12	0.95 Mg
Weldalite 049	5.4	1.3	0.14	0.4 Ag 0.4 Mg

1.3.1 Current Usage

Aluminum-lithium alloys have not yet received the widespread usage and acceptance hoped the commercial producers. However, some aluminum-lithium alloys have been utilized on recent commercial jetliner airframes and the material is used significantly in the EH101 helicopter. In addition, several AL-LI alloys are “under consideration” for a wide variety of developmental and experimental aircraft and space vehicles. The cost of Al-Li alloys is typically three to five times that of the conventional aluminum alloys they are intended to replace. This is due partly to the relatively high cost of Lithium and also to high processing and handling costs for the material.

1.3.2 Metallurgy and Properties

The lithium content of wrought Al-Li alloys cannot exceed the solubility limit of 4.2% Li in aluminum. In practice, the Li content is generally less (except in certain powder-metallurgy materials discussed later.) Lithium is the lightest metallic element. It has an atomic mass of about 7 g/mol, a solid density of 0.534 g/cm³ at 20oC, a BCC crystal structure and a melting temperature of 181oC. Elemental aluminum has a FCC crystal structure and a solid density of 2.7 g/cm³ at 20oC. Each 1% of lithium reduces the density of an AL-Li alloy by about 3% and increases the stiffness by about 5%.

High strength AL-Li alloys are obtained by precipitation heat treatments similar to those used for conventional al-alloys, with some variations. Many of the AL-Li alloys achieve peak strength only if cold-work (stretching) is performed prior to the precipitation, or age-hardening, treatment. Furthermore, ancillary key alloy elements, such as zirconium (Zr) are added to control the grain microstructure during heat treatment. The mechanical properties of some nearpeak aged hardened (-T8x) AL-Li alloys are given in the table below.

TABLE 2: MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF TYPICAL NEAR-PEAK AGED AL-LI ALLOYS

Alloy	Density (g/cm ³)	Ductility (El %)	Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Longitudinal K _{1c} (MPa m ^{1/2})	Melting Temperature (oC)
2090	2.59	3-6	76	500	44	580-660
2091	2.58	6	75	550	>130	560-670
8090	2.55	4-5	77	480	75	600-655

Alloy 2090 was developed as a replacement for 7075-T6, offering 8% lower density and 10% higher stiffness than the conventional alloy that is used heavily in aircraft structures. The 2090 alloy also offers superior corrosion resistance in salt-spray (marine) environment than 7075-T6.

Alloy 2091 was developed as a replacement for conventional aluminum alloy 2024-T3,

offering 8% lower density and 7% higher modulus as well as superior damage tolerance.

Alloy 8090 was developed as a replacement for some of the longest serving of the commercial aluminum alloys, namely 2014 and 2024. Alloy 8090 has 10% lower density and 11% higher modulus than these conventional counterparts, and 8090 exhibits superior mechanical properties at cryogenic temperatures.

The alloy that is marketed under the trade name Weldalite 049, as its name suggest, is a weldable Al-Li alloy designed to replace 2219 and 2014 in spacecraft launch systems. The density of Weldalite 049 is 2.7 g/cm³ (about the same as its conventional counterparts), it has about 5% higher modulus than 2024, and tensile strengths of forged parts in excess of 700 MPa have been reported.

The success of failure of the current applications of these advanced alloys will likely determine their engineering significance in the long-term.

1.3.3 Applications

Aluminum lithium alloy used in,

- wing sections on the U.S. Air Force F-15 Eagle fighter jet, such as the upper inboard aft wing skin
- forgings for the wheels and brakes of aircraft
- the inner wheel half of the Boeing 757 jet aircraft

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

There are many research oriented studies are carried out in aluminum lithium alloys. In our project we combined all the above to big one roof and study their characteristics,

(i) Thomas M. Holmes and Ernest S. C. Chin(Materials Producability Branch),Paul J. Huang(Metals Research Branch),Robert E. Pasternak(Materials Testing And Evaluation Branch) has conducted a research on the topic of Evaluation of 8090 and weldalite-049 aluminumlithium alloys(1992). This paper gives following results and discussions,

- Both 8090-T8771 and Weldalite-T8 Al-Li alloys demonstrate superior strength to weight ratios compared to the 2519-T87 and 5083-H131 aluminum alloys. The 8090 possesses comparable mechanical properties while providing an 8% reduction in density over 2519. The Weldalite has a comparable density as 2519 but demonstrates improvements of over 25% in yield strength, ultimate tensile strength and fracture toughness.
- The two Al-Li alloys display significantly improved axial fatigue properties over 2519-T87 and 5083-H131 aluminum plates. The Weldalite plates and 8090

extrusions demonstrated an increase in excess of 150% and 50%, respectively, in the fatigue limit compared to 2519.

- Both 8090 and Weldalite provide ballistic properties comparable to the 2519 and 5083 aluminum alloys against both AP and FSP projectiles. Both Al-Li alloys fall within the range of scatter for the 2519 alloy, yet above the range of the 5083 data.

(ii) Aman Aggarwal (Dept. of Mechanical and Automation Engineering, Maharaja Agrasen Institute of Technology, Rohini, Delhi, India) and Hari Singh (Department of Mechanical Engineering, National Institute of Technology, Kurukshetra, India) has conducted a research on the topic of Optimization of machining techniques (2005). This paper gives following results and discussions,

- A review of literature shows that various traditional machining optimization techniques like Lagrange's method, geometric programming, goal programming, dynamic programming etc. have been successfully applied in the past for optimizing the various turning process variables.
- Fuzzy logic, genetic algorithm, scatter search, Taguchi technique and response surface methodology are the latest optimization techniques that are being applied successfully in industrial applications for optimal selection of process variables in the area of machining.
- Taguchi methods and response surface methodology are robust design techniques widely used in industries for making the product/process insensitive to any uncontrollable factors such as environmental variables. Japanese companies such as Nippon Denso, NEC, and Fugitsu have become world economic competitors by using the Taguchi approach that has potential for savings in experimental time and cost on product or process development and quality improvement. There is general agreement that off-line experiment.

(iii) A.Arsecularatnea, L.C.Zhanga, C.Montrossb (a school of Aerospace, Mechanical and Mechatronics Engineering, Sydney) has conducted a research on the topic of Wear and tool life of tungsten carbide, PCBN and PCD cutting tools. This paper gives following results and discussion,

- In this work, tool wear mechanisms for three tool/work material combinations were considered. It was concluded that, under practical conditions, the dominant wear mechanism for WC/steel is diffusion while that for PCBN/hardened-steel is chemical wear. For this latter tool/work combination, it was also found that the available tool temperature and tool life results could be represented very well using an Arrhenius

type rate equation for chemical wear.

(iv) N.Eswara prasad and A.A.Gokhale (Defence Metallurgical Research Laboratory, P.O,Kanchanbagh, Hyderabad, India) and P. Rama rao (Jawaharlal Nehru Centre for Advanced Scientific Research, Jakkur, Bangalore, India) has conducted a research on the topic of Mechanical behavior of aluminium–lithium alloys. This paper gives following results and discussion,

- Al–Li alloys are prime candidate materials to replace traditionally used Al alloys. Despite their numerous property advantages, low tensile ductility and inadequate fracture toughness, especially in the through thickness directions, militate against their acceptability.
- Extensive co-planar slip, sensitivity towards the presence of even low contents of alkali metals, hydrogen and some of the impurities are key factors responsible for the property limitations.
- It is now possible to obtain alloys in different thermal and thermomechanical conditions that are suitable for different product forms. However, further efforts are needed to suitably modify the microstructure and crystallographic texture in order to improve isotropic mechanical behavior and enhance damage tolerance of these alloys.

(v) A. Heinz, A. Haszler & C. Keidel, Hoogovens Aluminium (Rolled Products now part of Corus Group Plc, Koblenz, Germany) and S. Moldenhauer, R. Benedictus & W.S. Miller (Hoogovens Research & Development now part of Corus Group Plc, CA IJmuiden, The Netherlands) has conducted a research on the topic of Recent development in aluminum alloys for aerospace applications. This paper gives following results and discussion,

- The new high strength thick plate products developed at Hoogovens Aluminum Rolled Products, Koblenz enable the aircraft manufactures requirement of improved fatigue, higher damage tolerance and virtually distortion free machining to be met in plate products up to 280 mm in thickness.
- Developments in 2000 series damage tolerant sheet enable extreme dimension sheet (3.2_12.7 m) to be produced within the 2024 chemistry window with high toughness and fatigue crack growth performance.
- Co-operation of material suppliers with aircraft manufactures enables the development of ‘novel’ alloy combinations so that new joining technologies can be taken advantage of whilst improving overall product performance at lower overall cost.

(vi) S.R.Das and R.P.Nayak (Department of mechanical engineering, OEC, Bhubaneswar, India) and D.Dhubal (Department of mechanical engineering, Indira Gandhi institute of technology, Sarang, Odisha) has conducted a research on the topic of Optimization of cutting parameters on tool wear and work piece surface temperature in turning of AISI D2 steel.

This paper gives following results and conclusion,

- The experimental results showed that the Taguchi parameter design is an effective way of determining the optimal cutting parameters for achieving low tool wear and low workpiece surface temperature.
- The percent contributions of depth of cut (60.85%) and cutting speed (33.24%) in affecting the variation of tool wear are significantly larger as compared to the contribution of the feed (5.70%).
- The significant parameters for workpiece surface temperature were cutting speed and depth of cut with contribution of 41.17% and 34.45% respectively. Although not statistically significant, the feed has a physical influence explaining 21.58% of the total variation.
- The predicted optimal range of tool wear is $0.21 \leq \mu TW \leq 0.31$ and for workpiece surface temperature is $37.51 \leq \mu T \leq 43.21$.
- The relationship between cutting parameters (cutting speed, depth of cut, feed) and the performance measures (tool wear and workpiece surface temperature) are expressed by multiple regression equation which can be used to estimate the expressed values of the performance level for any parameter levels.

3. REQUIREMENTS FOR MACHINING ALUMINIUM ALLOYS

3.1 MINIMIZE BUILD UP EDGE

When machining aluminum, one of the major failure modes of cutting tools is the material being machined adheres to the tool cutting edge. This condition rapidly degrades the cutting ability of the tool. The built-up edge that is generated by the adhering aluminum dulls the tool so it can no longer cut through the material. Tool material selection and tool coating selection are the two primary techniques used by tool designers to reduce the occurrence of the built-up edge.

Two different carbide materials used in high-speed machining tools are sub-micron grain and coarse grain. Sub-micron grain carbide material has generally been accepted as the preferred material of choice because it is very hard and maintains a sharp cutting edge. When machining aluminum at very high speeds, however, this conventional wisdom is incorrect.

The sub-micron grain carbide material requires a high cobalt concentration to achieve the fine

grain structure and the material's strength properties. Cobalt reacts with aluminum at elevated temperatures, which causes the aluminum to chemically bond to the exposed cobalt of the tool material. Once the aluminum starts to adhere to the tool, it quickly forms a built-up edge on the tool rendering it ineffective.

The secret is to find the right balance of cobalt to provide adequate material strength, while minimizing the exposed cobalt in the tool for aluminum adherence during the cutting process. This balance is achieved using coarse-grained carbide that provides a tool of sufficient hardness so as to not dull quickly when machining aluminum while minimizing adherence.

3.2 TOOL SELECTION

The tool design element that must be considered when trying to minimize the built-up edge is the tool coating. Tool coating choices include TiN, TiCN, TiAlN, AlTiN, chrome nitrides, zirconium nitrides, diamond and diamond-like coatings (DLC). With so many choices, aerospace milling shops need to know which one works best in an aluminum high-speed machining application.

The Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) coating application process on TiN, TiCN, TiAlN, and AlTiN tools makes them unsuitable for an aluminum application. The PVD coating process creates two modes for aluminum to bond to the tool—the surface roughness and the chemical reactivity between the aluminum and the tool coating.

The PVD process results in a surface that is rougher than the substrate material to which it is applied. The surface “peaks and valleys” created by this process causes aluminum to rapidly collect in the valleys on the tool. In addition, the PVD coating is chemically reactive to the aluminum due to its metallic crystal and ionic crystal features. A TiAlN coating actually contains aluminum, which easily bonds with a cutting surface of the same material. The surface roughness and chemical reactivity attributes will cause the tool and work piece to stick together, thus creating the built-up edge.

The diamond and DLC coatings result in a very smooth chemically inert surface. These coatings have been found to significantly improve tool life when cutting aluminum materials.

The diamond coatings were found to be the best performing coatings, but there is a considerable cost related to this type of coating. The DLC coatings provide the best cost for performance value, adding about 20 percent to 25 percent to the total tool cost. But, this coating extends the tool life significantly as compared to an uncoated coarse-grained carbide tool.

Finally the authors select the three types of tungsten carbide tools,

- Tungsten carbide (no coated)
- Tungsten carbide coated with Aluminum oxide (wc+AL2O3)
- Tungsten carbide coated with Titanium nitride (wc+TiN)

3.3 FACTORS AFFECTING THE SURFACE FINISH

Whenever two machined surfaces come in contact with one another the quality of the mating parts plays an important role in the performance and wear of the mating parts. The height, shape, arrangement and direction of these surface irregularities on the workpiece depend upon a number of factors such as:

- The machining variables which include,
 - a) Cutting speed
 - b) Feed
 - c) Depth of cut.
- The tool geometry:

The design and geometry of the cutting tool also plays a vital role in determining the quality of the surface. Some geometric factors which affect achieved surface finish include:

- a) Nose radius
 - b) Rake angle
 - c) Side cutting edge angle, and
 - d) Cutting edge.
- Workpiece and tool material combination and their mechanical properties
 - Quality and type of the machine tool used,
 - Auxiliary tooling, and lubricant used, and
 - Vibrations between the workpiece, machine tool and cutting tool.

4. INTRODUCTION TO MINIMUM QUANTITY LUBRICATION

FIGURE 3: MINIMUM QUANTITY LUBRICATION LAYOUT

This setup consists of following accessories for attaining MQL

- 1) Compressor
- 2) Storage tank
- 3) Electric motor
- 4) Centrifugal pump
- 5) Mixing chamber
- 6) External nozzle

4.1 COMPRESSOR

The process of increasing the pressure of air, gas or vapor by reducing its volume is called *compression* and the device used to carry on this process is called *compressor*.

A machine which takes air or gas during suction stroke at low pressure and then compresses it to high pressure in a piston – cylinder arrangement is known as *reciprocating compressor*.

Compressor is a machine that used for increase the pressure of the air. The compressor may be low pressure generated up to 7 bar is enough to run this project.

The compressor used in here is reciprocating type, single cylinder & single acting air compressor with following specifications.

Power : 1 HP

Capacity :	3.4 cu / ft
Work pressure`:	7 kg / cm ²
Design pressure:	14 kg / cm ²

FIGURE 4

4.1 STORAGE TANK

The storage tank used here is made up of steel. This tank is cylindrical in shape with four openings (ports).

- Port 1 is at top of the tank used to supply the lubricant into the cylinder from the pump.
- Port 2 is used to supply the air from the compressor and it is situated at side of the tank.
- Port 3 is also at side of the tank which used for output from the cylinder has the mixture of compressed air and lubricating oil.
- Port 4 is situated at bottom of the tank used for remove the lubricating oil from the tank when this setup is not in use.

SPECIFICATION:

The specification of the storage tank used in this setup is follows,

Radius of the storage tank (R)	= 0.125 m
Length of the storage tank (L)	= 0.55 m
W.K.T volume of the cylinder (V)	= $\Pi R^2 L / 2$
	$V = \Pi \times (0.125)^2 \times 0.55 / 2$
	$V = 13.498 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$
	$V = 13.498 \text{ liters.}$

FIGURE 5

4.2 ELECTRIC MOTOR

The main application of electric motor is to run the centrifugal pump that used for supplying lubricant oil in to the storage tank.

The specification of the electric motor is as follows,

Power : 0.5 HP OR 0.37 kw

Revolution (RPM) : 2800 RPM

Amps : 2.5 A

Head : 33 m

Quantity : 30 LPM

FIGURE 6

4.3 CENTRIFUGAL PUMP

- The name centrifugal (C.F) pump to this pump is because of the use of principle of centrifugal

force in this pump ($v^2 = 2gh$).

- Centrifugal pump is a machine that imparts energy on the fluid to flow from higher level to low level or vice versa.
- C.F pump is extremely simple machine that consists of two basic parts namely impeller and casing.
- It is filled with fluid when impeller rotated and this rotation imparts on the fluid causes it to exits on the impeller vanes with higher velocity then it entered in the pump.
- This outward flow reduces pressure at the impeller eye, allowing more fluid to enter.
- The liquid that exits the impeller is collected in the casing where its velocity is converted into pressure before it leaves the pump's discharge.
- This pump is has a foot valve which connected to the sump of the lubricating oil tank. The output of the pump is connected to the port 1 of the storage tank. The pump here is used is centrifugal because it can be run on no load condition.

FIGURE 7

4.4 MIXING CHAMBER

- We use the mixing chamber in order to mix the lubricant with the compressed air.
- This mixing chamber is made of a special type material and also it has three ports.
- One is the inlet from the storage tank that has the mixture of lubricating oil and compressed air.
- Another port is situated at extreme end that is connected to the inlet of the nozzle.
- The third port has the connection of another compressed air connection because of most efficient mixing of air and lubricating oil.

FIGURE 8

4.5 NOZZLE

The coolant nozzle plays a critical role in the proper supply of coolant. It must accurately direct an adequate flow with sufficient velocity directly at the Tool - Workpiece interface and must resist vibration, swarf and inertial forces that could knock it out of alignment. Nozzle is a duct of varying cross sectional area in which the velocity increases with the corresponding drop in pressure. Its main function is increases velocity.

FIGURE 9

MLQ SETUP

The minimum quantity lubrication setup was fabricated for economize the coolant fluid which is used in semi-automatic lathe. It located in Valivalam polytechnique college, Nagapattinam.

MLQ SETUP

FIGURE 10

5 TURNING PROCESS PARAMETERS

FIGURE: 11

The parameters for machining can be classified as follow:

1. **Machine based parameters:** These are spindle speed, feed rate, depth of cut and cutting tool.
2. **Coolant based parameters:** These are the supply of coolant, type of coolant.
3. **Workpiece based parameters:** These are the workpiece geometry, dia. of workpiece, chemical composition of the workpiece material.
4. **Cutting tool base parameter:** These are the material to tool, shape of tool, nose radius of tool. The parameters selected for this study based on the availability of these parameters on the machine were - Cutting Tool, Cutting Fluid, Spindle Speed, Feed and Depth of Cut.

Here, we can now that the cutting tool has only single degree of freedom while other four factors we selected has two DOF.

$$\text{Therefore, Total DOF} = (1*1) + (2*4) = 9$$

Five factors with different numbers of levels have been selected for this experimentation. This experiment is carried out in all geared lathe.

5.1 LATHE SPECIFICATIONS

The lathe machine used here is a 1987 model semi-automatic all geared lathe. This lathe is situated in Valivalam Polytechnic College, Nagapattinam.

By selecting three speed and constant feed rate and a depth of cut in that machine. The feed and speed rate can be changed by changing gear lever in that lathe. Its specifications are

Manufacture	:	Madras machine tool manufactures limited, Coimbatore.
Type	:	170 G 2
Year	:	1987
Size	:	1960
RPM	:	65-1000
Cross slide	:	260 mm

FIGURE 12

TOOL HOLDER

To use a cutting tool within a semi-automatic lathe machine there is a basic holder required to mount it on the machines spindle or turret.

FIGURE 13

5.2 TURNING TOOLS AND ITS SPECIFICATIONS

Tungsten carbide is an inorganic chemical compound (specifically, a carbide) containing equal parts of tungsten and carbon atoms. In its most basic form, tungsten carbide is a fine gray powder, but it can be pressed and formed into shapes for use in industrial machinery, cutting tools, abrasives, armorpiercing rounds, other tools and instruments, and jewelry.

Sintered tungsten carbide cutting tools are very abrasion resistant and can also withstand higher temperatures than standard high speed steel tools. Carbide cutting surfaces are often used for machining through materials such as carbon steel or stainless steel, as well as in situations where other tools would wear away, such as high-quantity production runs. Because carbide tools maintain a sharp cutting edge better than other tools, they generally produce a better finish on parts, and their temperature resistance allows faster machining. The material is usually called cemented carbide, hard metal or tungsten-carbide cobalt: it is a metal matrix composite where tungsten carbide particles are the aggregate and metallic cobalt serves as the matrix. Manufacturers use tungsten carbide as the main material in some high-speed drill bits, as it can resist high temperatures and is extremely hard.

Carbide is more expensive per unit than other typical tool materials, and it is more brittle, making it susceptible to chipping and breaking. To offset these problems, the carbide cutting tip itself is often in the form of a small insert for a larger tipped tool whose shank is made of another material, usually carbon tool steel. This gives the benefit of using carbide at the cutting interface without the high cost and brittleness of making the entire tool out of carbide. Most modern face mills use carbide inserts, as well as many lathe tools and end mills. In recent decades, though, solid-carbide end mills have also become more commonly used, wherever the application's characteristics make the pros (such as shorter cycle times) outweigh the cons (mentioned above).

5.2.1 Tungsten Carbide

Tungsten carbide cutting tools are very abrasion resistant and can also withstand higher temperatures than standard high speed steel tools.

Specification

- Molecular Formula : WC
- Appearance : Grey – Black lustrous solid
- Melting point : 2870°C

5.2.2 Tungsten Carbide Coated with Aluminum Oxide

The most chemically resistant tool materials are oxides, which display negligible solubility in alloy at any practicable machining speed. Aluminum oxides has the abrasive wear resistance to perform effectively in the machining of alloy.

Specification

- Molecular Formula : WC + Al₂O₃
- Appearance : Black lustrous solid
- Melting point : 2960°C

5.2.3 Tungsten Carbide Coated with Titanium Nitrate

Recently, the technology of producing wear-resistant coatings of titanium nitrate on high speed steel tooling has been widely adopted. Because the hot hardness of high speed steel tooling does not exceed 700 °C, the effect of abrasion is expected to contribute significantly to the wear of coatings on high speed steel substrates and an analytical model of the cutting process that is useful in designing improved coatings for the effects of both abrasion and chemical dissolution.

Specification

- Molecular formula : WC + TiN
- Appearance : gold lustrous solid
- Melting point : 3250°C

FIGURE 14

5.3 ALUMINIUM LITHIUM ALLOY (8090) COMPOSITIONS

Specifications:

Al	- 95.18%
Cu	- 1.3%
Li	- 2.45%
Zr	- 0.12%
Mg	- 0.95%

Dimensions:

Diameter	: 25 mm
Length	: 300mm

FIGURE 15

4 CHIP TOOL INTERFACE TEMPERATURE

This is measured by the **infrared optical thermometer**. It has a laser point source detection and temperature is measured by passing infrared rays over the source destination and accurate temperature of that point is shown in the digital indicator. This infrared temperature indicator measures the temperature in the range of **-50°C to 550°C**.

FIGURE 16

5.5 CHIP MORPHOLOGY

This chips during every parameter change in turning are collected separately in a stick cover for taking chip morphology test. The formation of chips during machining reveals the mechanism of metal cutting. Continuous chips are produced while machining ductile material with proper cutting conditions. Normally machining harder materials discontinuous chips are produced. These chips are having impact on the surface produced, temperature developed and power required for the machining. In the present investigation, the authors have carried out the analysis of the chips produced in hard turning of hard chrome plated surfaces. The study of chips is vital for the optimizing the machining conditions.

FIGURE 17

5.6 SURFACE ROUGHNESS TESTING

Surface roughness is a measure of the workpiece surface finish. The roughness of a surface affects the friction because when something is rough and you put friction to it, it creates sparks while smooth surfaces when friction is added causes a slight static shock. This surface roughness is measured at Metrology laboratory, Department of production engineering, JJ college of Engineering and technology, Trichy.

SPECIFICAIONS

Make	: Mitutoyo Corporation.
Detection method	: Differential Inductive methods.
Detector drive range	: 0-21mm (.82in)
Stylus Material	: Diamond
Tip radius	: 5 μ m (200 μ in)
Measuring force	: 4mN (0.4gf) (0.75mN (0.075gf) (0.75mN
measuring	Force type)
Radius of skid curvature	: 40mm (1.57in)
Detector retraction	: Stylus op
Transverse speed	: Measurement: 0.25mm/s. 0.5mm/s (.01in/s, 02in/s)
Return	: 0.8mm/s (.03in/s)

SURFACE ROUGHNESS TESTER

Surface roughness tester is the machine which used to measure the roughness of the surface using probes. Roughness is nothing but the frictional force applied by the surface to the adjacent surface. If roughness increases the amount of frictional force increases.

FIGURE 18

6. METHODOLOGY

We have 300mm aluminum lithium alloy which is divided into 9 segments with 30mm each, the corresponding are numbered according to the machining.

6.1 WORK PIECE LAYOUT

DRY:

<i>FACE</i>	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
-------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

WET:

<i>FACE</i>	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
-------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Dividing the aluminum lithium alloy we get extra 10mm for holding in the chuck on the lathe. Also its face are noted. This notation will be helpful for finding the operation number noted as 1, 2, 3 etc.

The tool used here is multi point cutting (quadrilateral shape tool). Hence a single tool can be used for four cutting process because it has four cutting points. Tool layout is given below,

6.2 TOOL LAYOUT

FIGURE 19

In the above fig. the cutting tool specification with the operation number that correspondingly matches with segment number in the aluminum lithium alloy is noted.

6.3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP (TAGUCHI L9 METHOD)

Setup: 1

SL.NO	TOOL.NO	SPEED	FEED	DEPTH	COOLANT
1	T1	S1	F1	D	DRY
2	T2	S1	F2	D	DRY
3	T3	S1	F3	D	DRY
4	T1	S2	F2	D	DRY
5	T2	S2	F3	D	DRY
6	T3	S2	F1	D	DRY
7	T1	S3	F3	D	DRY
8	T2	S3	F1	D	DRY
9	T3	S3	F2	D	DRY

Setup: 2

SL.NO	TOOL.NO	SPEED	FEED	DEPTH	COOLANT
1	T1	S1	F1	D	WET

2	T2	S1	F2	D	WET
3	T3	S1	F3	D	WET
4	T1	S2	F2	D	WET
5	T2	S2	F3	D	WET
6	T3	S2	F1	D	WET
7	T1	S3	F3	D	WET
8	T2	S3	F1	D	WET
9	T3	S3	F2	D	WET

Setup: 3

SLNO	TOOL.NO	SPEED	FEED	DEPTH	COOLANT
1	T1	S1	F1	D	MQL
2	T2	S2	F2	D	MQL
3	T3	S3	F3	D	MQL
4	T4	S4	F4	D	MQL
5	T5	S5	F5	D	MQL
6	T6	S6	F6	D	MQL
7	T7	S7	F7	D	MQL
8	T8	S8	F8	D	MQL
9	T9	S9	F9	D	MQL

6.4 SPEED & FEED PARAMETERS

We take three speed and feed rate during machining. This speed are taken based on maximum speed, average speed and minimum speed. The depth of cut is constant. Hence here three parameters are taken into account while machining.

1. Speed (S1) = 290 RPM,
2. Speed (S2) = 465RPM,
3. Speed (S3) = 740 RPM,
4. Feed (F1) = 0.193mm/Rev,
5. Feed (F2) = 0.243mm/Rev,
6. Feed (F3) = 0.304mm/Rev,

7. Depth of cut (D) = 0.5mm.

7. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

In this process we can take three speeds ranges, feed and constant depth of cut. This process is done on lubricant conditions. The lubricant conditions are referred as MQL, the machining is done on the semi-automatic lathe the feed are given gear and engagement easily. As the aluminum lithium alloy is fixed in the lathe chuck then tool is fixed in the tool holder and process is carried out.

In this following experiment we have analyzed the three parameters namely chip tool interface temperature and surface roughness.

Temperature is taken with help of infrared optical thermometer which is a noncontact type. Using that experiment temperature during turning is measured at three different places and that average is taken approximately as a result.

Surface roughness test is done on the perthometer. Using perthometer tip that made contact with the specimen at different places and its valve are noted.

This valve is averaged and tabulated in the below tabular column.

S.NO	Tool	Speed (rpm)	Feed (mm/Rev)	Depth (mm)	Coolant	Time (min)	Temp (°c)	MRR (g/s)	Surface roughness test (µm)
1	WC	290	0.193	0.5	DRY	0.32	32.7	0.1	1.79
2	WC	465	0.243	0.5	DRY	0.15	33.9	0.212	2.23
3	WC	740	0.304	0.5	DRY	0.7	30.9	0.456	2.98
4	WC+Al ₂ O ₃	290	0.243	0.5	DRY	0.32	33.5	0.1	2.16
5	WC+Al ₂ O ₃	465	0.304	0.5	DRY	0.14	33.1	0.228	2.82
6	WC+Al ₂ O ₃	740	0.193	0.5	DRY	0.11	32.7	0.290	3.60
7	WC+TiN	290	0.304	0.5	DRY	0.18	34.2	0.177	1.11
8	WC+TiN	465	0.193	0.5	DRY	0.20	34.5	0.16	1.65
9	WC+TiN	740	0.243	0.5	DRY	0.9	33.1	0.355	2.21
10	WC	290	0.193	0.5	MQL	0.32	32.2	0.1	1.92
11	WC	465	0.243	0.5	MQL	0.15	33.3	0.212	2.05
12	WC	740	0.304	0.5	MQL	0.7	34.7	0.456	3.20

13	WC+Al ₂ O ₃	290	0.243	0.5	MQL	0.32	34.2	0.1	1.95
14	WC+Al ₂ O ₃	465	0.304	0.5	MQL	0.14	33.4	0.228	2.75
15	WC+Al ₂ O ₃	740	0.193	0.5	MQL	0.11	32.9	0.290	3.62
16	WC+TiN	290	0.304	0.5	MQL	0.18	33.9	0.177	1.45
17	WC+TiN	465	0.193	0.5	MQL	0.20	33.6	0.16	2.09
18	WC+TiN	740	0.243	0.5	MQL	0.9	33.2	0.355	2.71

S. N O	Tool	Speed (rpm)	Feed (mm /Rev)	Depth (mm)	Coolant	Time (min)	Temp (°c)	MRR (g/s)	Surface roughness test (µm)
19	WC	290	0.193	0.5	WET	0.32	33.9	0.1	1.79
20	WC	465	0.243	0.5	WET	0.15	30.9	0.212	2.23
21	WC	740	0.304	0.5	WET	0.7	33.5	0.456	2.98
22	WC+Al ₂ O ₃	290	0.243	0.5	WET	0.32	33.1	0.1	2.16
23	WC+Al ₂ O ₃	465	0.304	0.5	WET	0.14	32.7	0.228	2.82
24	WC+Al ₂ O ₃	740	0.193	0.5	WET	0.11	34.2	0.290	3.60
25	<u>WC+TiN</u>	290	0.304	0.5	WET	0.18	34.5	0.177	1.11
26	<u>WC+TiN</u>	465	0.193	0.5	WET	0.20	33.1	0.16	1.65
27	<u>WC+TiN</u>	740	0.243	0.5	WET	0.9	32.7	0.355	2.21

7.1 TUNGSTEN CARBIDE (WC)

7.1.1 Temperature

FIGURE 20

7.1.2 Surface Roughness

FIGURE 21

7.2 TUNGSTEN CARBIDE COATED WITH ALUMINUM OXIDE

7.2.1 Temperature

FIGURE 22

7.2.2 Surface Roughness

FIGURE 23

7.3 TUNGSTEN CARBIDE COATED WITH TITANIUM NITRATE

7.3.1 Temperature

FIGURE 24

7.3.2 Surface Roughness

FIGURE 25

8. METAL REMOVAL RATE

FIGURE 26

9. CONCLUSIONS

Following are the conclusions drawn based on the test conducted on Aluminum lithium (8090) alloy during turning operation with Tungsten carbide.

1. From the results obtained from Surface Roughness tester, the value of Surface Roughness was calculated which depend on Cutting Speed, Feed and Depth of Cut.
2. From Taguchi orthogonal array method (L9), based on the ranking it can be concluded that **Feed** has a greater influence on the Surface Roughness followed by Speed. Depth of Cut had least influence on Surface Roughness.
3. The optimal settings of process parameters for optimal Surface Roughness are: **Speed (290 rpm), feed (0.304 mm/rev) and DOC (0.5 mm)**. This research gives us how Taguchi's parameter design to obtain optimum condition with lowest cost, minimum number of experiments and Industrial Engineers can use this method.
4. By using MQL system, it saves **50%** of coolant which done for machining and also reduce environmental problems.
5. In this research, **tungsten carbide coated with titanium nitrate (wc+ TiN)** gives better surface finish and MRR in both dry and wet conditions.

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REFERENCES

1. Akhyar G., Haron C.H.C, Ghani J.A, (2008), "Application of Taguchi method in the optimization of turning parameters for surface roughness", *International Journal of Science Engineering and Technology*, 1(3), pp. 1379-1385.
2. Alaxender. A, Varadarajan. A.S, Philip. P.K, (1998), "Hard turning with minimum cutting fluid: a viable green alternative on the shop floor", in *Proceedings of the 18th AIMTDR*, pp. 152–155.
3. Arsecularatnea. J.A, Zhanga. L.C, Montrossb. C, (2006), "Wear and tool life of tungsten carbide, PCBN and PCD cutting tools", *International Journal of Machine Tools & Manufacture*, pp. 482–491.
4. Das. S.R, Nayak, D.Dhubal. R.P, (Dec 2012), "Optimization of cutting parameters on tool wear and work piece surface temperature in turning of AISI D2 steel" *International Journal of Lean Thinking* volume3, issue2.
5. Eswara Prasad. N, Gokhale. A.A, Rama rao, P, (2003), "Mechanical behavior of aluminium lithium alloys", *Sadhana Vol. 28, Parts 1 & 2*, pp. 209–246.
6. Heinz, A, Haszler. A, Keidel. C, Moldenhauer. S, Benedictus. R, (2000), "W.S. Miller,
7. "Recent development in aluminum alloys for aerospace applications", *Materials Science and Engineering*, A280, pp. 102–107.
8. Klocke. F, Eisennblatter. G, (1997), "Dry cutting", *Ann. CIRP* 46 (2), pp. 519–526.
9. Mani lavanya. K, Suresh. R.K, Sushil Kumar Priya. A, Diwakar Reddy. V, (May. - Jun. 2013), "Optimization of Process Parameters in Turning Operation of AISI-1016 Alloy
10. Steels with CBN Using Taguchi Method and Anova", *IOSR Journal of Mechanical and Civil Engineering (IOSR-JMCE)*, Volume 7, Issue 2, pp. 24-27.
11. Rajput, "Thermal engineering", S. Chand publishers, 2000.
12. Thomas M. Holmes, Ernest S. C. Chin Paul, J. Huang, Robert E. Pasternak, (1992),
13. "Evaluation of 8090 and weldalite-049 aluminum-lithium alloys" U.S. Army materials technology laboratory, Massachusetts, pp. 92-59.